

Impact of Perceived Influence and Supervisor Supportiveness on Employees' Innovative Behavior Special Reference on Hotel Industry in Batticaloa District

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Abstract

The Hotel industry plays a crucial role in the country's economic development. This study investigates the impact of Perceived Influence (PI) and Supervisor Supportiveness (SS) on Employees' Innovative Behavior (EIB) special reference on Hotel Industry in Batticaloa District. This quantitative study aims to address this gap by analyzing survey data collected from 329 employees across five major classes of Hotels in Batticaloa District. The independent variables of Perceived Influence (PI) are measured through three dimensions and Supervisor Supportiveness (SS) is measured through five dimensions. The dependent variable of Employees' Innovative Behavior (EIB) that contribute directly to the Hotel's technical operations, organizational environment. Stratified sampling method used to make the sampling frame and quantitative research approach was used. The variables such as Perceived Influence (PI), Supervisor Supportiveness (SS) and Employee's Innovative Behavior (EIB) are well defined and explained the relationship, develop hypotheses as well as test the hypotheses and collection of quantities data are measured. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analyses. According to the findings, used to find out which variable is closely associated with Employee Innovative Behavior (EIB). This analysis was made to investigate the relationship between variables of Perceived Influence (PI), Supervisor Supportiveness (SS) and Employees' Innovative Behavior (EIB). Examining the mechanism of how employee Innovative Behavior impact workplace wellbeing is of considerable significance. Therefore, findings of this study assist employees to develop their Innovative Behavior.

Keywords: *Employees' Innovative Behavior, Perceived Influence, Supervisor Supportiveness*

Background of the study

Hospitality is a key component of Sri Lanka's culture and plays a significant role in the country's tourism sector and economy. The tourist industry contributes better to the economy and society in a number of ways than any other sector of the economy. The Eastern Sri Lanka is a great area to explore, with great beaches like Pasekudaha and Arugam Bay. For organizations to achieve results in an environment with never experienced changes, such as the COVID19 pandemic, innovative behavior is desperately needed from employees who plan and implement new ideas and tasks quickly. Many scholars claim that innovative behavior significantly impacts organizational performance through previous studies (Choi & Kang, 2021). Supervisor supportiveness moderates the relationship between employees' perceived influence in the workplace and their levels of innovative behavior. The aim of this study was to contribute to the field in this domain by examining how employees' influence in the workplace and supervisor supportiveness interact to stimulate employees to engage in an innovative course of action, or inhibit them from doing so. Knowledge of this impact of influence and supervisor supportiveness was developed by using a sociopolitical approach to employee innovation.

Research Problem statement

Innovative ideas are fundamental thing for changes in the organizations. With the increasing demand for global tourism, more restaurants, accommodations, modes of transportation, and entertainment businesses have emerged, causing huge competition in the hospitality industry. In (Kim & Koo, 2017) proved the existence of a positive correlation between employee innovative behavior and job performance. The findings of this study suggest that hotel employees are engaged in their job and are more innovative when they perceive a high quality of LMX.

The study of (Zhao, Liu, Zhang, Xu, & Liu, 2022), explores the internal mechanism explaining the impact of perceived respect on innovative behavior. Perceived respect on innovative behavior, which broadens the research on the antecedents of innovative behavior. Employees who perceive that they are respected in the workplace gain a sense of membership, recognition, and psychological safety; therefore, they show increased loyalty and a sense of responsibility toward the organization (Grover, 2014). Most studies focused on the benefits of such behavior to

individuals or organizations, no study carried out the relationship among the variables in the hotel industry. Therefore, this study is in order to fill research gap in this research area.

Significance of the study

This research identifies the impact of perceived influence and supervisor supportiveness on employee innovative behavior of hotels in Batticaloa. Therefore, findings of this study assist employees to develop their innovative behavior. Furthermore, these research facilities the hotels to identify the level of employee innovative behavior regarding their working practices and how supervisor support exists to their innovative actions presently. This research also guides the management to identify the staff's motivation and training which they needed. It helps employees to be more creative and innovative in their work. Therefore, they can provide better as well as quality service to the customers. The context of highly valued innovation and workplace wellbeing, examining the mechanism of how employee innovative behavior impact workplace wellbeing is of considerable significance.

Scope of the study

In this study the dependent variable employees' innovative behavior and independent variables are perceived influence and supervisor supportiveness. The research study will include classification of hotels in Batticaloa district. The respondents are the employees in that particular hotels and the research will be undertaken in Batticaloa for collecting the actual data from 329 samples that represent the target population. The relevant to the research is gathered through both primary and secondary data sources. The quantitative research design will be used to collect the primary data and the secondary data collection sources include such as, text book, journal and websites.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To identify the levels of perceived influence, supervisor supportiveness and employee innovative behavior on Hotels in Batticaloa.
2. To identify the relationships among perceived influence, supervisor supportiveness and employee innovative behavior on Hotels in Batticaloa.

3. To explore the impacts of perceived influence and supervisor supportiveness on

employee innovative behavior on Hotels in Batticaloa.

Conceptual framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework (Source: (Janssen, 2005))

Perceived influence

(Scott & Bruce, 1994), Employees' perception of respect enables them to experience their own value, pursue higher needs, exert their potential, and guide themselves to carry out more innovative behavior. Perceived influence is an individual's subjective perception of the possibility of obtaining and maintaining (current or future) employment, which has gradually become an important personal resource to help employees adapt to the uncertain workplace environment. From the perspective of enterprises, high employability awareness may stimulate high job turnover of employees, which leads enterprises into the risk of training and development costs being wasted (Jeff Sakaki, 2022).

Supervisor supportiveness

When an employee received supervisor support to the optimum tell, he or she will consider that as recognition for his efforts. Employee will consider their supervisor as the working representative on behalf of organizations (Baran, Shanock, & Miller, 2012). Hospitality industry managers have high expectations for new employees to quickly learn job characteristics to contribute to improving performance and service quality. The hotel industry is a service industry

that offers room service, food and beverage providers, and other services to the general public, which are managed commercially (Ketut Astawa, Ni Luh Ek Armoni, & Suardani, 2023).

Employees' innovative behavior

Innovative behavior is an act of generating, promoting and application of innovative thinking in the organization for the purpose of personal and organizational performance, which enables employees to use innovative ways of thinking, quickly and accurately respond to customer demand changes (Scott & Bruce, 1994). (Janssen, 2005) argues that psychological contract employees perceived which means their organizational commitment level, determines whether they engaged in innovation activities. The dimensions of innovative work behavior have not been seen in the work implementation of all employees at the locus of this research.

The employee's innovative behavior is defined as: In the work process, employees generate innovative ideas or solutions to problems, and efforts will be paid to the practice. The motivation of employee's innovative behavior can be divided into internal and external factors. Internal factors refer to innovative personal traits and ability to participate in innovation, and external factors including the open team environment, the support of leaders. Under the mutual working of internal and external factors, the innovative efficacy and creative willingness of employees have been improved (Xiangyin & Yishuang, 2014).

Methodology

The research methodology constitutes the internal environment by understanding and identifying the right type of research, strategy, philosophy, time horizon, approaches, followed by right procedures and techniques based on his or her research work (Sam Gounder, 2012). Research philosophy is associated with assumption, knowledge and nature of the study. It deals with the specific way of developing knowledge. The research philosophy of this study was positivism because in this study the role of the researcher is limited to data collection and interpretation through objective approach and the research findings are usually observable and quantifiable. The assumption is independent of and neither affects nor is affected by the subject of the research.

Quantitative data uses deductive approach. Quantitative data requires statistical analysis to test hypotheses. In addition, deduction from general perspectives leads the researcher to develop a theoretical framework (hypotheses) and test it thereby concluding a specific conclusion. Based on this approach the variables such as Perceived Influence, Supervisor Supportiveness and Employees' Innovative Behavior are well defined and explained the relationship, this study has used a survey strategy. Survey strategy is usually associated with the deductive approach and this study design used cross sectional studies because a study undertaken in which data are gathered just once, perhaps over a period of days or weeks or months, in order to answer a research question. The study was quantitative research and designed to combine primary survey based data with secondary information from other related institutions. The study's findings can be applied to or used for this group, and they are the main group that the research is about. Populations help define the study's limits and give the reader clues about the surroundings and context as well as the opportunity to focus on specific areas within a predetermined scope (Dalowar Hossan, Zuraina Dato Mansor, & Nor Siah Jaharuddin, 2023). The Employees' of Hotels in Batticaloa district were the study's target populations and the researcher was concerned of the study's population, which includes of 1850 employees at hotels in Batticaloa district of Sri Lanka.

The sampling process for this research involved a selection of a sufficient number of elements from the population, **Slovin's formula** was used to determine the sample size for the study's objectives. With the use of **Slovin's formula**, a researcher may accurately sample the population.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

n = Number of samples or sample size

N = Total population

e = Error tolerance

$$n = \frac{1850}{1 + [1850 \times (0.05^2)]} = 328.88 = 329$$

n = Number of samples or sample size (329)

N = Total population (1850)

e = Error tolerance (0.05)

Received: 01 December 2025

Revised: 05 December 2025

Accepted: 06 January 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14609627](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609627)

Out of these 1850 employees, only 329 were selected as sample by using stratified random sampling method. The random sampling method was applied to select the sample of employees as the population framework was clearly identified. Then simple random sampling, a subset of individuals (a sample) chosen from larger set (a population). Each individual is chosen randomly and entirely by chance, such that each individual has the same probability of being chosen at any stage of sampling process.

$$\text{no of samples} = \frac{\text{Employees of particular hotel}}{\text{Employees of all hotel}} \times 329$$

The respondents had to be employed by one of a selected hotel in the Batticaloa district in order to qualify for the sample. The number of responders who chose from each hotel is shown in table 4.1 below.

Table 1. Sample Distribution among Hotel Employees

Hotel Classification	Hotel's Name	No. of Employees	Sample Size of Employees	Total Sample No. of Employees
5 Star Hotel	Uga Bay	240	43	143
	Sun Siyam	200	36	
	Aki Villa	180	32	
	Anilana	180	32	
4 Star Hotel	The Calm Resort & Spa	70	12	124
	Aqua Marine Beach Resort	50	9	
	Maalu Maalu Resort & Spa	150	27	
	Amaya Beach	250	44	
	Anantaya Resort & Spa	180	32	
3 Star Hotel	Hotel East Lagoon	50	9	44
	Ametheyst Resort	80	14	
	Laya waves	70	12	
	Earl's Red	50	9	
2 Star Hotel	Rivira Resort	30	5	12
	Green Garden	25	4	
	Sunny Fish Hotel & Resort	10	2	
	Inn On the Bay	5	1	

1 Star Hotel	Treatoo Hotel	12	3	6
	Nirmaa Shadow Inn	10	2	
	New Sunrise Hotel	8	1	
Total				329

(Source: Collected from hotels)

This study was carried out based on primary data. The data were collected 329 capturing only the employees in hotels. For those reasons, questionnaire was issued to the employees in ordered to collect data the questionnaire has been used. The questionnaire is a tool that contains more questions used to collect the data. In general, closed questions are included to express their views throw on the topic of interest as freely as possible. This questionnaire contains two parts,

- **Personal information of the employees in hotels**

It requires some data related to the gender, age, marital status, religion, district, education and working related information such as, job position, department, hotel classification, experience and salary. In the first part of questionnaire, there are eleven questions and all of them are required to mark.

- **General research information**

Which will be measured by Likert’s scale of 1-5 ranges from “Very dissatisfied” to “Very satisfied”. Questionnaire consists of research information in part 2. The respondents were asked to mark their choice in suitable box.

Table 2. Scale of Measurement

Levels	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
Scale Value	1	2	3	4	5

(Source: Developed for the study purpose)

Methods of data analysis

The samples of data collected were analyzed according to the descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis. Descriptive analysis depicts the mean and standard deviation for the analysis of research data using SPSS 23.0 software package;

1. Cronbach's alpha for reliability of the questionnaire

Based on (George & Mallery, 2003), Cronbach's alpha coefficient (CAC) ranges vary from 0 to 1 and values close to one indicating high consistency, and value close to zero indicating no consistency.

2. Frequency and descriptive analysis tools

When consider the results derived of research questions how the respondents react or agree with those particular statements.

3. Univariate analysis

Based on, Univariate analysis technique was used for evaluating respondents' views. It looks at the range of value, as well as the central tendency of the values including mean and standard deviation for PI, SS and EIB.

4. Pearson coefficient correlation for testing the relationship among variables

The relationship between these two variables is described here by a single value, the coefficient.

5. Regression analysis for testing the impact of the variables

It aids in determining the strength and statistical significance of the impact.

Results and discussion

Reliability analysis

Reliability test is significant to determine the reliability and validity of measurement which have been used in this study. Reliability concerns the extent to which a measurement of a phenomenon provides stable and consist result. Testing for reliability is important as it refers to the consistency across the parts of a measuring instrument (Hamed Taherdoost, 2016). The reliability of the instrument was measured using Cronbach's Alpha analysis. It measures the internal consistency of the instrument, based on the average inter item correlation.

Table 3. Reliability analysis for the overall variables

<i>Variables</i>	<i>No. of items</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha value</i>
<i>Perceived Influence</i>	3	0.920
<i>Supervisor Supportiveness</i>	5	0.867
<i>Employees' innovative behavior</i>	17	0.936

(Source: Survey Data)

Here, all variable has Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.75. Therefore, all items consider in this study are to be reliable. Which suggest that the internal reliability of instrument for satisfactory.

Research objective 1: To identify the levels of Perceived influence, Supervisor supportiveness and Employees' innovative behavior on Hotels in Batticaloa

The univariate analysis used to measure the level of contribution of all variables. It used for this study and descriptive statistic used to find out the mean values and standard deviation of the variable.

Table 4. Level of Perceived influence, Supervisor supportiveness and Employee innovative behavior

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Decision attribute</i>
<i>Perceived influence</i>	3.73	1.06	High
<i>Supervisor supportiveness</i>	3.86	0.81	High
<i>Employee innovative behavior</i>	4.13	0.73	High

(Source: Survey Data)

According to the descriptive analysis results, the mean value of PI, SS and EIB are 3.73, 3.86, 4.13 respectively. Which has fall within the range of $3.51 < X \leq 5.0$. It shows employees have high level of PI, SS and EIB at their Hotels. It can be divide $\pm X$ around the mean value ($SD=X$). The results support with empirical findings of (Janssen, 2005).

Research objective 2: To identify relationship among perceived influence, supervisor supportiveness and employees’ innovative behavior on Hotels in Batticaloa

The correlation analysis used to find out which variable is closely associated with employee innovative behavior. This analysis was made to investigate the relationship between variable namely perceived influence, supervisor supportiveness and employee innovative behavior.

Table 5. Correlation among Perceived influence, supervisor supportiveness and Employees’ innovative behavior.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Innovative Behavior</i>	
<i>Perceived Influence</i>	<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	<i>0.751</i>
	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	<i>.000</i>
	<i>N</i>	<i>329</i>
<i>Supervisor Supportiveness</i>	<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	<i>0.807</i>
	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	<i>.000</i>
	<i>N</i>	<i>329</i>

The correlation coefficient (r) value was 0.751 between PI and EIB at the significant level (p = 0.000). It shows that there is a strong positive relationship exists between PI and EIB among the employees of selected hotels in Batticaloa district according to the data analysis. Further, the correlation coefficient between the SS and EIB is 0.807 at the significant level (p = 0.000). It can be seen that there is a strong positive relationship exists between the study variables among the employees of selected hotels in Batticaloa district.

Research objective 3: To explore the impacts of perceived influence and supervisor supportiveness on employees’ behavior on Hotels in Batticaloa

Bivariate analysis is used to measure the objective under the simple liner regression and multiple regression analysis were used to measure the impact of perceived influence and supervisor supportiveness on employee innovative behavior on hotels in Batticaloa.

Simple regression of Perceived influence and Employee innovative behavior

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Sig. F Change
1	.751 ^a	.565	.563	.48666	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), PI

As depicted in Table, the regression model shows that the adjusted R-value of 0.565 in the model indicates that 56.5% of the observed variance in employees’ innovative behavior can be explained by the independent variable namely, perceived influence among the employees of selected hotel in Batticaloa district.

Hypothesis Testing 1

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.202	.098		22.519	.000
Perceived Influence	.519	.025	.751	20.589	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Innovative behavior

According to the B value of perceived influence is 0.519. Its means if PI increased by one-point employee EIB increased by 0.519.

• **Simple regression model: $Y = 2.202 + .519X_1$**

If the significance of p value is less than 0.05 it shows the significance between two variables. Based on regression results indicate that significant of p value is less than 0.05 (p=.000). So PI is significantly influence on EIB. Therefore, it can be concluded there is enough evidence to say there is a positive relationship between PI and EIB.

Simple Regression of Supervisor supportiveness and Employees’ Innovative Behavior

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Sig. F Change
1	.807 ^a	.651	.650	.43555	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Supervisor Supportiveness

Based on the Table, the “R Square” statistic indicated that the 65% of the variation in the employees’ innovative behavior of employees is explained by supervisor supportiveness. This is considered as large in order words the independent variables of supervisor supportiveness in the regression model account for 65% of the total variation in the employees’ innovative behavior. Adjusted R – Square is 0.65 which implies that 65% of change in employees’ innovative behavior is explained by supervisor supportiveness.

Hypothesis Testing 2

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.314	.117		11.254	.000
	supervisor supportiveness	.730	.030	.807	24.708	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employees’ Innovative Behavior

According to the B value of SS is 0.730. its means if SS increased by one-point EIB increased by 0.730.

• **Y = 1.314 + 0.730X₂**

If the significance of p value is less than 0.05. it is shows the significance between two variables. Based on regression results indicate that significant of p value is less than 0.05 (p= .000) So, SS

is significantly influence on EIB. Therefore, it can be concluded there is enough evidence to say there is a positive relationship between SS and EIB.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

From the estimation, it may be able in conclude that the impact of perceived influence and supervisor supportiveness on employees' innovative behavior of employees. It was based on a sample of 329 employees from hotels in Batticaloa district. To accomplish the following study goals, the researcher in this instance has employed descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, and regression analysis. The employees have high level of perceived influence, supervisor supportiveness and employees' innovative behavior in hotels. According to the findings, the researcher can indubitably that employees' innovative behavior is in high. A correlation analysis was conducted to obtain the desired findings, and the study allowed the researcher to deduce the associations shown below. While there is a strong positive relationship between PI and EIB ($r = 0.751$, $p 0.000$), and there is a strong positive relationship between SS and EIB such as, ($r = 0.807$, $p 0.00$). Results of this study have some clear implications for the improvement of employees' innovative behavior.

Recommendations of the Study

Supervisors should give their employees' well-being the highest preference of employees working that helps to increase employees' innovative behavior on hotel industry. Improving employee's participation will not only provide more realistic view of what is possible to achieve, it will also create the opportunities for employee to put forward new ideas and be more creative in helping their hotel achieve Business objectives. Supervisor's behaviors, collaborative working behaviors with subordinates, create a good relationship among the employees. therefore, it is recommended that supervisor supportiveness play important to encouraging the employees to innovative behavior. it is recommended that supervisor's creative behaviors, critical thinking and innovative ideas helps to increase the employee satisfaction that is tend to be an employees' innovative behavior.

Limitations of the Study

Therefore, conclusions may not be extrapolated to other industries or organizations. The researcher solely concentrated on a small number of factors in the current investigation. There may be other factors that might affect an employees' innovative behavior. The study's quantitative methodology is yet another drawback. If qualitative research methods like interviews and observation were utilized instead, it would be useful to learn more about how willing employees were to change. Only the quantitative data that was gathered using structured questionnaires was used for the analysis in this study. Five-point scales were utilized to evaluate the study questions. Gender, age, education level, work experience, job position, working department and salary weren't distributed fairly in the study. Another drawback to this study is its use of cross-sectional data, which might make it difficult to draw firm conclusions regarding causality.

Direction for Future Research

Future studies can be carried out in different industries, such as insurance, financial institutions, banks and government and private offices. rather than in same sector and should select a larger sample. In order to examine the association between perceived influence, supervisor supportiveness and employees' innovative behavior, it is preferable to include any other factors. Re-evaluate and broaden the ideas, frameworks, or models that the research has used. This study can be expanded with qualitative elements to provide further justifications. This study's cross-sectional methodology shows that respondents' data was collected at a particular moment in time. To provide reliable results, a four-point scale can be added to this survey. Since there is no neutral, the respondent can provide a more accurate response.

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